

Addenda to the conoidean gastropods of the outer continental shelf and slope off Galicia (NW Iberian Peninsula)

Adiciones a los gasterópodos conoideos de la plataforma y talud continental de Galicia (Noroeste de la Península Ibérica)

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ABSTRACT

Four species of conoidean gastropods (*Gymnobela lamyi*, *Phymorhynchus chevreuxi*, *Theta chariessa* and *Xantodaphne* cf. *dalmasi*) are added to those recorded in a previous work on circalittoral and bathyal bottoms off the Galician continental margin. Data on three other previously mentioned species (*Typhlomangelia nivalis*, *Austrobela pyrrhogramma* and *Gymnobela abyssorum*) found in the same sample are also added.

RESUMEN

Se añaden cuatro especies más de gasterópodos conoideos (*Gymnobela lamyi*, *Phymorhynchus chevreuxi*, *Theta chariessa* y *Xantodaphne* cf. *dalmasi*) a las citadas en un trabajo anterior en fondos circalitorales y batiales del margen continental gallego. Además se aportan nuevos datos de tres de las especies ya citadas (*Typhlomangelia nivalis*, *Austrobela pyrrhogramma* y *Gymnobela abyssorum*) y encontrados en la misma muestra que las anteriores.

KEY WORDS: Mollusca, Raphitomidae, Northeast Atlantic.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Mollusca, Raphitomidae, Atlántico nororiental.

INTRODUCTION

After the publication of OLIVER *ET AL.* (2022) on conoidean gastropods from off Galicia, we found additional specimens overlooked during sorting, all coming from the same sampling station. Some of the shells belonged to four species not mentioned in the previous work, along with three species already recorded. We provide here these new data, which expand the knowledge of

this gastropod group on the outer continental shelf and slope off Galicia.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

All the specimens studied come from the same sample collected during the campaign "A Selva 2008". This campaign was held in July 2008 on the

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vessel *R/V Sarmiento de Gamboa* in the fishing area called "A Selva" located in the Northwest of Galicia (within the coordinates 43°30'N-44°15'N; 08°10'W-09°10'W) spanning the continental shelf and slope (depths between 149 and 2516 m), with bottoms containing extensive carbonated hard grounds.

General data related to this campaign were published by ALDEA ET AL. (2010). That sample was SE/08 DRN 30-1 (23/07/2008, coordinates 43°48.73'N; 08°51.94'W) collected by means of a Naturalist Dredge (DRN) at 576-612 m depth in a bottom of phosphorites and carbonate crusts.

SYSTEMATIC PART

Unrecorded species

Gymnobela lamyi (Dautzenberg, 1925) (Fig. 1A-D)

Pleurotoma lamyi Dautzenberg, 1925: 2, figs 3-4; 1927: 61, pl. 3, figs 12-13.

Gymnobela lamyi (Dautzenberg) — BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980: 53, fig.117 holotype).

Type locality: Near Azores Islands (38°35'N - 28°06'W, -1250 m)

Material examined: One shell (9.0 × 4.5 mm).

Description (based on the studied material): Shell ovate-biconical, fragile, semi-translucent, with a relatively short spire, distinctly shouldered, with a slightly concave subsutural ramp, and inflated last whorl (reaching nearly 80% of the total height), with a short 'spout-like' siphonal canal (Fig. 1A-D). Sculpture of more or less equally spaced axial ribs and spiral cords narrower than their interspaces, defining an almost square cancellation, with projecting intersections of ribs and cords. Ribs orthocone, forming a receding sinus over the subsutural ramp, which lacks spiral cords (secondary cords appear between primary cords in the holotype, BOUCHET & WARÉN, 1980, fig. 117). Aperture wide, ovate (60% of the shell

height). Inner lip covered by a callus; outer lip thin, sharp edged.

Protoconch multispiral, yellowish with brown apex, with curved opisthocline ribs that run the entire height of the whorls and other, less defined prosocline ribs in its lower part, which together with the former form a rhomboidal reticulation on the lower half of the whorl.

Remarks: This species was hitherto known only from the holotype and eight additional shells, all collected in the same station off the Azores Islands. The shell studied here, with three teleoconch whorls, is most likely a juvenile when compared to the holotype.

The generic placement of *Gymnobela lamyi* is tentative (BOUCHET & WARÉN,

(Right page) Figure 1. Shells from sample SE/08 DRN 30-1 (576-612 m off Galicia. A-D (570-: *Gymnobela lamyi*, shell (9.0 × 4.5 mm), protoconch and detail of the sculpture of the teleoconch; E-H: *Phymorhynchus chevreuxi*, shell (13.5 × 7.1 mm) and detail of the sculpture of the teleoconch; I-J: *Theta chariessa*, shell (16.1 × 8.5 mm); K-N: *Xanthodaphne cf. dalmasi*, shell (9.5 × 5.0 mm), protoconch detail of the sculpture of the beginning of the teleoconch.

Figura 1. Conchas de la muestra SE/08 DRN 30-1 (576-612 m) frente a Galicia. A-D: Gymnobela lamyi, concha (9,0 × 4,5 mm), protoconcha y detalle de la escultura de la teleoconcha; E-H: Phymorhynchus chevreuxi, concha (13,5 × 7,1 mm) y detalle de la escultura de la teleoconcha. I-J: Theta chariessa, concha (16,1 × 8,5 mm); K-N: Xanthodaphne cf. dalmasi, concha (9,5 × 5,0 mm), protoconcha y detalle de las escultura del inicio de la teleoconcha

1980). The genus *Gymnobela* Verrill, 1884 has been used to include a wide admixture of species of moderate sized, thin-shelled, ovate-biconical shells, with a relatively short spire, angular shoulder, and inflated last whorl with a short 'spout-like' siphonal canal, and a multispiral protoconch covered in diagonally cancellate sculpture (LANDAU ET AL., 2022). Recently, CRISCIONE ET AL.

(2021b) considered *Gymnobela* to be an artificial assemblage of several unrelated genus-level lineages, and they described some new genera to include several species from southern Australia. To one of them, *Austrobela*, they transferred the northeast Atlantic species previously named *Gymnobela pyrrhogramma* (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896).

Phymorhynchus chevreuxi (Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1897) (Fig. 1E-H)

Pleurotoma chevreuxi Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1897: 150-151, pl. III, fig. 2.

Phymorhynchus chevreuxi – BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980: 27, fig.71).

Type locality: Near Azores Islands (39°11'N - 29°06'W, -1600 m).

Material examined: One shell (13.5 × 7.1 mm)

Description (based on the studied material): Shell (Fig. 1E–G) fusiform, slender, buccinoid, ashen white, with more than three slightly convex whorls and concave subsutural ramp. Body whorl about 75% of the height of the shell. Sculpture of sharp and granulated spiral cords regularly spaced with wider interspaces in which growth lines are distinguished (Fig. 1H). Spiral sculpture on the last whorl of about twenty main cords, among which some secondary cords emerge. Aperture ovate (near 60% of the height of the shell); outer lip thin, fragile; columellar lip smooth, anterior part slightly curved. Siphonal canal short and wide, not recurved. Apex and

protoconch corroded which does not allow details to be observed.

Remarks: Like the previous species, *P. chevreuxi* is only known from type material from bathyal bottoms near the Azores islands. The genus *Phymorhynchus* includes about 20 known species, most of them common in vent/seep environments (WARÉN & BOUCHET, 2009; ZHANG & ZHANG, 2017). Three of the species of this genus were recorded by BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980), including *P. chevreuxi*. Two subfossil shells attributed to this genus were recorded previously in our previous work (OLIVER ET AL., 2022), but none of them correspond to *P. chevreuxi*.

Theta chariessa (Watson, 1881) (Fig. 1I-J).

Pleurotoma (Defrancia) chariessa Watson, 1881: 458-460.

Pleurotoma gisota Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1896: 412, pl.17, figs. 4-5.

Pleurotoma turrisulcatum Locard, 1897: 205-208, pl. 9, figs. 17-21.

Pleurotoma urinator Locard, 1897: 195-196, pl. 8, figs. 22-29.

Pleurotomella jeffreysii A.E. Verrill, 1885: 411-412, pl. 54, fig. 3.

Theta chariessa (Watson, 1881) – BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980: 59, figs. 14, 129-130, 254-255); CRISCIONE ET AL. (2021: fig. 15c, syntype).

Type locality: Stated by BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980) to be West of San Miguel, Azores, 38°30'N - 31°14'W, - 1800 m, but actually encompasses all the localities cited by Watson (1881) in the absence of a lectotype designation.

Material examined: One shell (16.1 × 8.5 mm).

Description (based on the studied material): Shell biconical, fusiform, somewhat glossy, carinated, with a wide concave subsutural ramp. Teleoconch of six regularly convex whorls. Body whorl nearly 75% of the height of the shell. Axial sculpture of weak axial riblets below the carina appearing as a series of prominent nodules; spiral sculpture absent except for weak spiral cords at the base at the level of the siphonal canal. Aperture suboval (about of 55% of the shell height), siphonal canal moderately long, columella straight, columellar callus thin and narrow. Protoconch multispiral, in a corroded state which does not allow to provide details.

Remarks: *Theta chariessa* resembles the type species of the genus, *T. lyronuclea* (Clarke, 1959), also with an amph-

atlantic distribution in both hemispheres (BOUCHET & WARÉN, 2020; SÁNCHEZ & PASTORINO, 2020). The genus *Theta* currently encompasses a total of six deep water species with a disjunct Atlantic/Pacific distribution (CRISCIONE *ET AL.*, 2021).

This species was described by WATSON (1881) from several localities: West Indies, Pernambuco, off Azores and Canary islands. It has already been found on the continental shelf of Galicia (43°24'N, 11°41'W) by the Travailleur 1882 expedition and it is widespread on both sides of the Atlantic in bathyal bottoms (BOUCHET & WARÉN, 1980). According to these authors, the species is quite variable, especially regarding its sculpture, with a complex synonymy.

Xanthodaphne cf. *dalmasi* (Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1897) (Fig. 1K-N)

Pleurotoma dalmasi Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1897: 153, lam. 3, fig. 4.

Pleurotoma dalmasi (Dautzenberg & H. Fischer) – BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980: 66, figs. 28, 137 holotype, 236-237); FIGUEIRA & ABSALÃO (2012: 10-11, figs 12-13).

Type locality: Off Azores, (40°05'N,- 27°28' W, -1850 m).

Material examined: One shell (9.5 × 5.0 mm).

Description (based on the studied material): Shell somewhat plump, white, with three evenly rounded teleoconch whorls and poorly differentiated subsutural ramp (Fig. 1K-L). Last whorl large, reaching about two-thirds of the total height. Aperture wide, oval, reaching near 60% of the total height, with a wide and short siphonal canal. Sculpture delicate, almost smooth, with sigmoidal growth lines and very fine spiral threads only visible at high magnification. At the beginning of the teleoconch, a growth line in an inverted C-shape can be seen outlining the anal sinus (Fig. 1N). Protoconch multispiral, light brown, with almost five whorls (Fig. 1M), with the characteristic diagonal cancellation in the lower half of the whorls formed by the intersection of complete opisthocline sinusoidal ribs and other incomplete orthocline ribs.

Remarks: *Xanthodaphne dalmasi* is known in deep bottoms of the northeast

Atlantic (Azores and Canary islands, Portugal) (BOUCHET & WARÉN, 1980), Mediterranean (BOUCHET & TAVIANI, 1989; MOYA-URBANO *et al.* 2023), and also recorded in the southwest Atlantic (Campos Basin) (FIGUEIRA & ABSALÃO, 2012).

We have identified this shell with doubts, since it is plumper than the holotype of *X. dalmasi*, species which is usually brown (not white). Its protoconch is somewhat different, with a less bulging nucleus. The shell illustrated by FIGUEIRA & ABSALÃO (2012) as *X. dalmasi* presents a more pronounced irregular spiral sculpture. The species *Xanthodaphne alessandropaglii* Nappo & Pagli, 2022, known from the Alboran Sea, Selvagens Islands and Bay of Biscay between 300 and 700 m in depth, is more fragile, translucent and its aperture does not reach 50% of the total height.

Species previously recorded

Typhlomangelia nivalis (Lovén, 1846) (Fig. 2A-C)

Material examined: One shell (14.0 × 7.0 mm).

Twenty shells (3 of them with soft parts) from several samples were recorded in the previous work in the depth range 411-1070 m (OLIVER ET AL., 2022). As commented there, according to BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980), this species shows great morphological variability, so it cannot be ruled out that this taxon

includes several cryptic species. This was already highlighted by LOCARD (1897), who described four different species now considered synonyms of *T. nivalis*. The shell here examined (Fig. 2A-C) is slightly different from the shells figured in our previous work and fits with *Pleurotoma neotericum* Locard, 1897.

Austrobela pyrrhogramma (Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1896) (Fig. 2D-G)

Material examined: Seven empty shells.

Seventeen shells (three of them with soft parts) were recorded in the previous paper found in samples from the 570-1300 m depth range (OLIVER ET AL., 2022). Seven

shells of this species collected at 576-612 m depth are here added to the studied area. It is also known in the Galicia Bank at 985-1000 m (GOFAS ET AL., 2021).

Gymnobela abyssorum (Locard, 1897) (Fig. 2H-M)

Material examined: Two empty shells.

Four specimens with soft parts and 7 empty shells collected between 566 and 1317 m were recorded in the previous

paper (OLIVER ET AL., 2022). This species was also found in the summit of the Galicia Bank at 985-1000 m (GOFAS ET AL., 2021).

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In the previous work on the conoidean gastropods found on the continental shelf and slope off Galicia, we recorded 38 species of 22 genera belonging to the families Cochlespiridae, Borsoniidae, Clathurellidae, Drilliidae, Horaiclavidae, Mangeliidae and Raphitomidae (OLIVER ET AL., 2022). Four additional species are recorded here (*Gymnobela lamyi*, *Phymorhynchus chevreuxi*,

Theta chariessa and *Xantodaphne* cf. *dalmasi*), all belonging to Raphitomidae and found in the same sample. Therefore, the number of species of conoidean gastropods in this area rises to 42, and the number of genera to 24. Likewise, the first two species mentioned above are recorded for the first time in Spanish waters, according to the national list of marine molluscs (GOFAS ET AL., 2017).

(Right page) Figure 2. Shells from sample SE/08 DRN 30-1 (576-612 m) off Galicia. A-C: *Typhlomangelia nivalis*, shell (14.0 × 7.0 mm); D-F: *Austrobela pyrrhogramma*, Shell (12.5 × 6.0 mm); G: *Austrobela pyrrhogramma*, shell (11.0 × 5.5 mm); H-J: *Gymnobela abyssorum*, shell (16.0 × 8.0 mm); K-M: *Gymnobela abyssorum*, shell (8.0 × 5.0 mm) and protoconch.

Figura 2. Conchas de la muestra SE/08 DRN 30-1 (576-612 m) frente a Galicia. A-C: *Typhlomangelia nivalis*, concha (14,0 × 7,0 mm); D-F: *Austrobela pyrrogramma*, concha (12,5 × 6,0 mm); G: *Austrobela pyrrogramma*, concha (11,0 × 5,5 mm); H-J: *Gymnobela abyssorum*, concha (16,0 × 8,0 mm); K-M: *Gymnobela abyssorum*, concha (8,0 × 5,0 mm) y protoconcha.

All but 8 species of conoidean gastropods recorded off Galicia, have been found in bathyal deeps beyond the edge of the continental shelf.

Three other previously mentioned species were also found now in this same sample (*Typhlomangelia nivalis*, *Austrobela pyrrhogramma* and *Gymnobela abyssorum*), in which *Spirotropis confusa* (Seguenza, 1880) and *Drilliola loprestiana* (Calcara, 1841) were also recorded (OLIVER ET AL., 2022). Therefore, in this same sample (collected in a bottom of phosphorites and carbonate crusts at 576-612 m depth) a total of 9 species of conoidean gastropods have been found. Seven of these species were represented by a single shell, proving the high diversity and the low abundance of these group of specialized predators in deep sea environments, as has been highlighted by different authors (i.e. SYSOEV, 1996; BOUCHET ET AL., 2009; KANTOR ET AL., 2016). Among conoideans, raphitomid snails are dominant in deep sea communities worldwide (CRISCIONE ET AL., 2021b), and so it happens in the studied area, where they represent half the number of total species, 21 from 42 (OLIVER ET AL., 2022; present paper).

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The high number of species found in the same sample, collected in the fishing area called "A Selva", points to the extraordinarily species richness of conoidean gastropods in this area, where 35 species of this group were found. In another of the previously studied samples from this area (sample DRN-7, 908-1100 m depth), up to 15 species were found (OLIVER ET AL., 2022).

Anyway, knowledge of the biodiversity of the deep sea remains very incomplete and fragmentary and requires a significantly greater sampling effort.

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